

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

**“Let’s Build our SFSC”
Event Validation Report
Responsible Partner: Q-PLAN**

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“Let’s Build our SFSC!” Event Validation Report - Greece

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of Q-PLAN for the organisation and validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event as online event in Thessaloniki, Greece organised on Thursday, March 3rd, 2023. This event is an online brokerage and networking event, to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agorBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agri-food sector at local level. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in Greece.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC” tool.
- **Annex** – Summary of the open discussion related to SFSC business models and their potential in the Greek agri-food market.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

“Let’s build our SFSC” is an online networking and matchmaking event to promote collaborations among producers and other value chain actors in the agri-food sector. The event was held on a Thursday evening at 17.00 – 19.15 local time. To support the main event goal for networking, the programme was structured using three main components and hosted in the online matchmaking platform that was selected as part of Task 3.4:

- **Main stage** featuring the event introduction and closing, instructions for using the platform and setting up one-to-one meetings, company presentations and an open discussion about SFSC business models with promising potential for the Greek agri-food sector.
- **Profiling and one-to-one networking area** where participants could create their networking profile, showcase their business and book meetings with other participants. The networking sessions were organised in 15-minute slots with 5-minute breaks in between. 3 slots were made available for each participant, in parallel with the company presentations in the main stage.
- **Helpdesk, set up as a break room** for participants to receive technical support and troubleshoot with the organising team, when arranging their one-to-one meetings. The helpdesk was available for the whole duration of the networking sessions.

The event programme is presented in more detail on the table below.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers/ Moderators	Location (Online)
Introduction	Introduction to the agroBRIDGES project and the purpose of the event	17.00 – 17.20	Eirini Efthymiadou (Q-PLAN)	Main stage
Open discussion	Short Food Supply Chains and their potential in Greece using an online whiteboard	17.20 – 17.50	Eirini Efthymiadou (Q-PLAN)	Main stage
Introduction to Brella networking	Instructions on how to find profiles, book and participate in one-to-one meetings, how to find the helpdesk.	17.50 – 18.00	George Malliopoulos (Q-PLAN)	Main stage
Company presentation	Wikifarmer: A B2B / B2C marketplace for agri-food products	18.00 – 18.20	Rodanthi Bampili (Content Creator)	Main stage

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers/ Moderators	Location (Online)
Networking slot #1	Parallel slot for 1:1 meetings	18.00 – 18.15	N/A	Networking area
Company presentation	TROPOS BRANDING Co.: Branding & marketing agency with experience in agrifood products.	18.20 – 18.40	Christos D. Katsanos (Co-owner)	Main stage
Networking slot #2	Parallel slot for 1:1 meetings	18.20 – 18.35	N/A	Networking area
Company presentation	AgroApps: A company that designs and develops technical solutions for the agrifood sector.	18.40 – 19.00	Dimitra Perperidou (Project Manager)	Main stage
Networking slot #3	Parallel slot for 1:1 meetings	18.40 – 18.55	N/A	Networking area
Future actions & closing	Final remarks and future agroBRIDGES activities, prompt to participants to provide their feedback	19.00 – 19.15	Eirini Efthymiadou (Q-PLAN)	Main stage

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

The event preparation and organisation required the involvement of two people from the Q-PLAN project team. There was no particular need for the involvement of specialised employees, however if this is possible, it would be recommended to best utilise available skills and expertise. The effort spent per activity is provided in the table below:

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Activity	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic / content design	1	Development / translation of promo material, registration forms, social media visuals, feedback form	In-house	1.5 person days

Activity	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Technical set up	1	Set up of event in matchmaking platform	In-house	2 person days
Technical testing	2	Testing of the online event setup	In-house	0.5 person days
Communications	1	Participants' and speakers' invitations, launch social media campaign	In-house	0.5 person day
Communications	1	Follow up and technical support / instructions for registration in matchmaking platform	In-house	2 person days
Session content	2	Presentations (introduction, closing), Brainstorming board	In-house	1 person day
Session moderator	2	Coordination of the online session	In-house	1.5 person days

2.3 Event material

The material developed for the event included material related with:

- the invitation and registration of participants and speakers,
- instructions for partners on setting up their networking profile on the matchmaking platform, as well as to find other participants and book one-to-one meetings.
- session content and presentation materials,
- event and evaluation feedback form,

Additional effort was needed to enter related information about the programme and sessions on the online matchmaking platform (Brella).

2.3.1 Invitation and registration material

The event invitation was designed using the templates developed by Q-PLAN for the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in all Beacon Regions. The material was customised to the needs of the Greek event and translated to Greek, as many farmers and producers in the region are not fluent in English at a professional level.

The **event invitation** was developed in the form of an email and also in the form of an official invitation letter, as presented in Figure 1, below.

The invitation provides important information about the event, including the date, time, scope and content of the event. Moreover, the event invitation provided a link to the online registration form for potential attendees.

The online registration form was developed following the respective template developed for “Let’s build our SFSC” events with a view to (i) **ensure controlled access to the online matchmaking platform**, as the maximum capacity per event was set to 50 participants and (ii) **to acquire the informed consent of participants** for the storage and processing of personal and professional data by the event organiser (Q-PLAN) and also for the exchange with other event participants for the networking sessions and (iii) to collect **relevant information for the publication of company / business profiles on the matchmaking platform**. The informed consent acquisition method was designed in line with the project’s Data Management Plan, the Ethics Requirements and relevant provisions of GDPR.

The online registration form was designed in Greek using [Cognito Forms](#) and is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Event invitation (in Greek)

Εκδήλωση δικτύωσης για παραγωγούς, επιχειρήσεις τροφίμων και εστίασης
Χτίζουμε βραχείες αλυσίδες εφοδιασμού τροφίμων

📅 Πέμπτη, 2 Μαρτίου ⌚ 17.00 – 19.30 📍 Online

Σας προσκαλούμε στην online εκδήλωση της Q-PLAN και του έργου agroBRIDGES που έχει σαν σκοπό να προωθήσει τη δικτύωση μεταξύ των παραγωγών και άλλων επαγγελματιών στην τοπική παραγωγή τροφίμων και εστίαση.

Ο βασικός στόχος της εκδήλωσης είναι να προωθήσουμε τη δημιουργία βραχέων εφοδιαστικών αλυσίδων τροφίμων, που βασίζονται στη συμμετοχή το πολύ ενός ενδιάμεσου μεταξύ των καταναλωτών και των παραγωγών.

Κατά τη διάρκεια της εκδήλωσης θα έχετε την ευκαιρία να:

- 👤 Γνωρίσετε άλλες επιχειρήσεις, δράσεις και επαγγελματίες από ομιλίες και παρουσίαση των προϊόντων / υπηρεσιών τους.
- 👥 Κάνετε ιδιωτικές συναντήσεις με επαγγελματίες και να συζητήσετε πιθανές συνεργασίες στο χώρο δικτύωσης της online πλατφόρμας της εκδήλωσης
- 👥 Παρακολουθήσετε και να συμμετέχετε στην ανοιχτή συζήτηση για τα επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα βραχέων αλυσίδων τροφίμων στην Ελλάδα

Αιτήσεις ανοιχτές μέχρι τις 28 Φεβρουαρίου ή μέχρι την κάλυψη του αριθμού των 50 διαθέσιμων θέσεων!

[Πατήστε εδώ για εγγραφή!](#)

agr BRIDGES Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Το έργο agroBRIDGES έχει λάβει χρηματοδότηση από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας «Horizon 2020» της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης με αριθμό σύμβασης 101000788.

Figure 2: Online registration form (in Greek)

Εγγραφείτε στην εκδήλωση του agroBRIDGES!

Online εκδήλωση δικτύωσης για παραγωγούς, επιχειρήσεις τροφίμων και επιχειρήσεις εστίασης.

Ημερομηνία: Πέμπτη, 2 Μαρτίου 2023 17.00 - 19.30

Τα προσωπικά σας στοιχεία

Θα χρησιμοποιήσουμε τα στοιχεία σας για να σας προσκαλέσουμε να εγγραφείτε στην online πλατφόρμα δικτύωσης της εκδήλωσης (Brella).

Όνοματεπώνυμο *	Το φύλο σας *
<input type="text" value="Πληκτρολογήστε το ονοματεπώνυμό σας"/>	<input type="text" value="Επιλέξτε από τη λίστα"/>
Το email σας *	Η δραστηριότητά σας *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="Επιλέξτε από την παρακάτω λίστα"/>

Προσωπικά δεδομένα και GDPR

Παρακαλούμε διαβάστε προσεκτικά την [Πολιτική Απορρήτου](#) του έργου agroBRIDGES και την [Φόρμα Ενημερωμένης Συγκατάθεσης](#) για τη χρήση και την προστασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων.

Δίνω τη συγκατάθεσή μου για την επεξεργασία των προσωπικών δεδομένων μου για τη:

- Συμμετοχή μου στην εκδήλωση δικτύωσης του έργου agroBRIDGES που διοργανώνει η Q-PLAN και την παροχή συστάσεων για βελτίωση της εκδήλωσης στο μέλλον.
- Συμμετοχή μου σε μελλοντικές δράσεις του έργου agroBRIDGES
- Λήψη μηνυμάτων και ενημερωτικών δελτίων (newsletters) σχετικά με τις δράσεις του έργου agroBRIDGES.

Αποστολή

[Αναφορά Κατάχρησης](#) | [Όροι Χρήσης](#)

A **social media campaign** was planned for the promotion of the event to a larger network of farmers, producers and agri-food chain actors in Greece. Relevant posts were planned for the Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn accounts. The social media post is provided as an example in the figure below.

The original campaign design consisted of the **event announcement** and **2-3 follow-up posts**, to promote the speakers and featured companies, as well as the final call for registration. Eventually, **the follow-up social media posts were suspended due to a large number of registrations, exceeding the event capacity**. More information on the promotional activities will be provided in Section 2.4.

Figure 3: Social media announcement on Q-PLAN's social media

2.3.2 Instructions for registering and using the online matchmaking platform

Following the initial registration of invitees, a set of practical instructions were developed to support attendees and speakers to register at the online matchmaking platform, to create their networking profile, find other businesses and individuals and suggest one-to-one meetings. The guidelines were developed in Greek using illustrations of the required steps to provide more intuitive guidance to participants.

Figure 4: Instructions for using the online matchmaking platform

Εκδήλωση δικτύωσης για παραγωγούς, επιχειρήσεις τροφίμων και εστίασης

Χτίζουμε βραχείες αλυσίδες εφοδιασμού τροφίμων

 Online

Αγαπητές και αγαπητοί συμμετέχοντες,

Για να παρακολουθήσετε την εκδήλωση θα χρειαστεί να κάνετε εγγραφή στην διαδικτυακή πλατφόρμα δικτύωσης **Brella** και να δημιουργήσετε το **προφίλ σας**.

Η δυνατότητα εγγραφής θα είναι διαθέσιμη μέχρι τις **28 Φεβρουαρίου** ή μέχρι την κάλυψη του αριθμού των **50 διαθέσιμων θέσεων!**

Οδηγίες για εγγραφή:

1. Μεταβείτε στο link της εκδήλωσης: <https://next.brella.io/join/agrobridgesGR>
Αν χρειαστεί, ενεργοποιήστε την αυτόματη μετάφραση γιατί κάποια σημεία της πλατφόρμας είναι στα Αγγλικά (για οδηγίες, δείτε στο τέλος της εικόνας)
2. Κάνετε εγγραφή με το λογαριασμό Google σας ή το email σας
3. Ακολουθήστε τα βήματα για να δημιουργήσετε το προφίλ σας

Αυτόματη μετάφραση στα ελληνικά:

Η εκδήλωση γίνεται στα ελληνικά, όμως η πλατφόρμα σε κάποια σημεία δυστυχώς δεν μας δίνει την επιλογή να μεταφράσουμε. Για όσες / όσους δεν γνωρίζουν αγγλικά, μπορείτε να χρησιμοποιήσετε τη σελίδα με αυτόματη μετάφραση

<p>Αν μπαίνετε από υπολογιστή: Πατήστε δεξί κλικ πάνω στη σελίδα στο Chrome και βρείτε την επιλογή «Μετάφραση στα ελληνικά».</p>	<p>Αν μπαίνετε από κινητό: Πατήστε τις τρεις τελείες στο πάνω δεξιά μέρος της οθόνης και θα έχει την επιλογή «Μετάφραση».</p>
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Βρείτε το μενού της εκδήλωσης:

Χρησιμοποιήστε το μενού στα αριστερά της σελίδας για να βρείτε όλες τις πληροφορίες που χρειάζεστε:

- Πρόγραμμα: Για να δείτε τις ομιλίες και το πρόγραμμα της εκδήλωσης

- Επιχειρήσεις: Για να δείτε τα προφίλ των εταιρειών που εκπροσωπούνται

- Άτομα: Εδώ θα βρείτε άλλους συμμετέχοντες και μπορείτε να κανονίσετε ατομικές συναντήσεις την ημέρα της εκδήλωσης

Οδηγίες για να κανονίσετε συναντήσεις:

1. Στην καρτέλα «Άτομα» θα δείτε τα προφίλ άλλων συμμετεχόντων

2. Αν σας ενδιαφέρει να μιλήσετε μαζί τους, πατήστε στο κουμπί “Chat / Suggest meeting” για να μιλήσετε ή να προτείνετε συνάντηση.

3. Επιλέξτε την ώρα που θέλετε να μιλήσετε.

Προσέξτε ότι μπορεί να μην είναι όλες οι επιλογές ώρας διαθέσιμες γιατί μπορεί το άτομο να έχει κλείσει άλλη συνάντηση.

3. Επιλέξτε την ώρα που θέλετε να μιλήσετε.

Μπορείτε να γράψετε ένα δικό σας μήνυμα στο γκρι πλαίσιο.

Όταν έχετε σιγουρέψει την επιλογή σας πατήστε το πράσινο κουμπί για να στείλετε το αίτημά σας.

2.3.3 Session content

As described previously, in Section 2.1, the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in Greece featured presentations and an open discussion except for the networking area for participants. The material was partly developed by the organising team while event speakers provided their own customised material. The following material was developed:

- **Introductory presentation (Q-PLAN)**
- **Online whiteboard (Q-PLAN):** An online whiteboard was designed using the [MURAL](#) tool. The online board focused on the 5 categories of SFSC business models: (i) direct sales, (ii) local food shops, (iii) online sales, (iv) logistics improvement, and (v) Community Supported Agriculture (CSA). The purpose was to assess whether they can be a promising alternative for Greek producers, to discuss their benefits and drawbacks and assess the profitability for producers (in absolute terms or in relation to conventional (long) food supply chains. An example of the online board format is provided in the figure that follows.

Figure 5: Online board to assess the potential of SFSC business model in Greece (Example: Community Supported Agriculture, in Greek)

Κοινωνικά Υποστηριζόμενη Γεωργία
Οι καταναλωτές αποκτούν συνιδιοκτησία στη διαχείριση της παραγωγής με αντάλλαγμα το δικαίωμα να προμηθεύονται προϊόντα.

Παραδείγματα

Καταναλωτές – συνιδιοκτήτες	Συνδρομή μέλους με αντάλλαγμα μέρους της παραγωγής	Εισφορά σε εργασία με αντάλλαγμα μέρους της παραγωγής
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Μπορεί να πετύχει στην Ελλάδα?

Ποια παραδείγματα έχουν περισσότερη πιθανότητα επιτυχίας?

Ποια είναι τα πλεονεκτήματα κατά τη γνώμη σας?

Ποια είναι τα μειονεκτήματα κατά τη γνώμη σας?

Είναι πιο κερδοφόρο σε σχέση με παραδοσιακές αλυσίδες εφοδιασμού? - Τι ποσοστό κέρδους κατά μέσο όρο?

- **3 Company presentations (Speakers)**
- **Concluding presentation (Q-PLAN)**

2.3.4 Event feedback form

Apart from the immediate benefits pursued through the organisation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” events for local stakeholders, i.e. opportunity of agri-food chain actors to meet with and discuss potential collaborations at a B2B level with a view to promote regional SFSC development, another important goal was to validate the event concept itself, gather feedback and evaluate lessons learnt to support other entities willing to use online networking events as a community engagement tool for the agri-food sector.

The event feedback form was designed following the template developed for all “Let’s build events” organised in the project’s Beacon Regions, to collect comparable evaluation data and propose improvements for this event concept. The questionnaire was short, including 6 questions and an open field for suggestions.

Cognito Forms was used to develop the digital questionnaire in the case of Greece. The online questionnaire is shown at the figure that follows.

Figure 6: Event evaluation form - Part 1 (in Greek)

Πείτε μας τη γνώμη σας για την εκδήλωση!

Η γνώμη σας θα μας βοηθήσει να βελτιώσουμε τον τρόπο που οργανώνονται αντίστοιχες εκδηλώσεις σε όλη την Ευρώπη!

Γνωρίζετε τι είναι οι βραχείες αλυσίδες εφοδιασμού τροφίμων πριν την εκδήλωση; *

- Ναι
- Όχι
- Δεν είμαι σίγουρη / σίγουρος

Σας βοήθησε η εκδήλωση να γνωρίσετε επαγγελματίες και επιχειρήσεις στην αγροδιατροφή που θα μπορούσατε να συνεργαστείτε; *

- Πολύ
- Αρκετά
- Ουδέτερο
- Λίγο
- Καθόλου
- Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Σας βοήθησε η εκδήλωση να δείτε τις Βραχείες Αλυσίδες Εφοδιασμού Τροφίμων ως πιθανή επιχειρηματική λύση; *

- Πολύ
- Αρκετά
- Ουδέτερο
- Λίγο
- Καθόλου
- Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Figure 7: Event evaluation form - Part 2 (in Greek)

Βρήκατε τις ατομικές συναντήσεις δικτύωσης χρήσιμες για να βρείτε και να συζητήσετε πιθανές συνεργασίες; *

- Πολύ
- Αρκετά
- Ουδέτερο
- Λίγο
- Καθόλου
- Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Σας βοήθησε η εκδήλωση να βρείτε ευκαιρίες για συνεργασία με άλλες επιχειρήσεις πάνω στις βραχείες αλυσίδες εφοδιασμού; *

- Πολύ
- Αρκετά
- Ουδέτερο
- Λίγο
- Καθόλου
- Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Θα θέλατε να διοργανώνονται παρόμοιες εκδηλώσεις στην περιοχή σας και πόσο συχνά; *

- Μηνιαία ή συχνότερα
- 3 - 4 φορές το χρόνο
- 2 φορές το χρόνο
- 1 φορά το χρόνο
- Ποτέ
- Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Αν θέλετε, παρακαλούμε αφήστε τα σχόλιά σας για την εκδήλωση:

Αποστολή

Figure 8: Event menu

2.3.5 Setting up the online environment of the event

The event was set-up online on the matchmaking platform, so that participants and speakers find relevant information about the event, such as sessions, speakers and material. Online information about the event was uploaded in Greek to further support attendees who do not speak English. Figure 8 shows the event navigation menu from the attendees’ perspective.

Moreover, company profiles were created if attendees were interested, using the information provided in the online registration form. The company profiles were created by the organising team to reduce the burden on attendees to manage information.

Attendees and speakers uploaded information about their personal profiles, their areas of interest so that they could find other people to network with via message or by booking one-to-one meetings on the day of the event, during the networking session.

The platform supported customised matchmaking categories to support people on finding the most relevant stakeholders to book meetings with. In the case of Greece, a bi-dimensional categorisation was used based on: (i) **the type of market actors** (producers, retailers/wholesalers, food processing, food packaging and HORECA, e-commerce, other) and (ii) **the product type** using 9 categories: fruit and fruit products, vegetables and herbs, milk and dairy, meat and meat products, olive oil and other fats, honey, nuts, wine & spirits, other.

Figure 9: Event breakout rooms

Figure 10: Online event schedule

Search by Session Name, Ομιλητές

X Clear filters

Thursday

Καλωσόρισμα

Eirini Efthymiadou (Speaker)
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Online
10min

Ανοικτή συζήτηση: Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα για βραχείες αλυσίδες εφοδιασμού τροφίμων στην Ελλάδα

Eirini Efthymiadou (Moderator)
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

George Malliopoulos (Facilitator)
Organiser - Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Online
30min

Ξενάγηση στην πλατφόρμα Brella

George Malliopoulos (Moderator)
Organiser - Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Online
10min

Παρουσίαση της εταιρείας Wikifarmer

Παρουσίαση της πλατφόρμας πώλησης τοπικών προϊόντων αγροδιατροφής για έλληνες παραγωγούς

Ροδάνθη Μπαμπίλη (Keynote speaker)
Content Manager - Wikifarmer

Online
20min

Show

Bookmarks

Past content

Show Time

Filter

Sessions & Meetings

Sessions

Meetings

Networking availability

Day

All days

Thursday 2nd March

Friday 3rd March

Locations

Online

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

Invitation and engagement process

The invitation process was unfolded in a series of steps, which were common for the event speakers and participants. The process was designed such as to ensure: (i) controlled access to the matchmaking platform, (ii) acquisition of informed consent for the storage, processing and sharing of personal data which is crucial for this type of event.

The invitation process is summarised in the graph below:

Figure 11: Invitation and engagement process

Event promotion

At least two weeks before the event and as soon as the final programme was ready, along with the necessary material and online setup (described in the previous sections), candidate speakers were approached and were introduced to the scope and topic of the event. The speakers were requested to prepare material to present their company and activities for a 20-minute session each.

As soon as the speakers started confirming their participation, the event was announced to the public. A social media announcement was launched using the social media accounts of Q-PLAN (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter) and the corporate website. The event was also promoted via the agroBRIDGES project channels.

In parallel, the invitation was promoted to members of the local network for further promotion, including speakers.

Figure 12: Event announcement on Facebook and Twitter

Figure 13: Event promotion on Facebook

The promotion of the event was also very actively supported by one of the presenting companies, Wikifarmer, which promoted the event on their website and also to wide network of producers and farmers all over Greece. The network of Wikifarmer responded very rapidly bringing more than 80 registrations over a period of less than two days.

Figure 14: Event promotion on wikifarmer.com

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The online networking event took place on Thursday, March 2nd, 2023, at 17.00 (local time) and had a duration of 2.5 hours. The main room was opened at least half an hour before the event, so that attendees and speakers join on time for the introduction.

3.1.1 Introductory session

During this first short session the organising team welcomed participants and speakers to the event. A short presentation of the agroBRIDGES project followed, while the scope and objective of the event was explained. The session concluded with a walkthrough of the event programme and upcoming sessions.

Figure 15: Snapshot from the agroBRIDGES project overview presentation

3.1.2 Open discussion about Short Food Supply Chain business models in Greece

During this 30-minute session, we discussed with attendees about the business models of SFSCs with greater potential within the Greek agri-food market. The discussion focused on 3 business models: (i) direct sales, (ii) local food shops, (iii) online sales. The other two business models were found to have more limited potential as, for instance, the ownership structure of the Community Supported Agriculture model is not supported by the Greek legal system. **The full discussion is summarised in the Annex of this report.**

Figure 16: Snapshot from the open discussion on SFSC business models (Part 1)

Figure 17: Snapshot from the open discussion on SFSC business models (Part 2)

3.1.3 Instructions for using the matchmaking platform & Networking area

During this session, participants were guided on how to use the matchmaking platform, find other people, set up and carry out one-to-one meetings to network with other producers. Information about navigation to and from the main stage, the helpdesk and the networking area was provided. At the end of this session and in parallel with company presentations, the three 15-minute networking slots were opened for one-to-one meetings.

Figure 18: Matchmaking platform walkthrough (Scheduling one-to-one meetings)

3.1.4 Company presentation – Wikifarmer

The online B2B marketplace of Wikifarmer was presented by **Rodanthi Babili, Content Manager of the Wikifarmer library**. The platform supports an extensive library for sharing knowledge on agricultural methods and products. The library is sustained by an in-house team of experts, external content writers and the community of producers/farmers. The marketplace of Wikifarmer supports more than 10000 registered producers and farmers in 6 countries of the Mediterranean, supporting transactions in wholesale and retail. The business models of Wikifarmer for suppliers and buyers (consumers, HORECA, industry, retail) were demonstrated. The presentation concluded with case studies to showcase the impact of Wikifarmer on business and sustainability in the agri-food sector. A discussion followed to clarify topics such as the local presence of Wikifarmer in markets beyond Greece, exports, distribution and delivery methods supported.

Figure 19: Snapshot from the presentation of Wikifarmer

3.1.5 Company presentation – TROPOS BRANDING Co.

The presentation of TROPOS BRANDING a branding strategy consultancy firm was delivered by Christos Katsanos, one of the co-owners and Brand Strategist. TROPOS BRANDING is supporting businesses to build their marketing, in the mid-term, and branding, in the long-term, that aims to build trust and show uniqueness, through product knowledge, traceability, location and storytelling, extending the capabilities of the products themselves.

The approach of TROPOS is aligned with five pillars that shape the modern (hybrid) era of branding and commerce: **connectivity** introducing new methods of communication and connection among people, **blockchain** introducing trust-based online transactions, **e-commerce** introducing new requirements in selecting promotion channels, pricing, packaging for (agrifood) products and know-how on the use of relevant infrastructure as well as the gradual transformation of social media platforms to e-commerce platforms, **tribes and microtribes**, small thematic groups of interest that people voluntarily join for mutual support, knowledge exchange forming the vital space of modern business branding, **metaverse**, the integration of the digital and physical world, that aims to solve time scarcity and physical limitations in commerce.

Figure 20: Snapshot from the presentation of TROPOS BRANDING Co.

3.1.6 Company presentation – AgroApps PC

The final presentation focused on AgroApps, based in Thessaloniki, that supports farmers and producers on the field with technological solutions related to crop management, monitoring and harvesting, supported by a team of diverse expertise such as agronomists, agroeconomists, geoanalysts, meteorologists, developers. AgroApps is also active in the field of Research and Innovation projects, two of them were presented: **enVision project** that employs methods for continuous monitoring of environmental practices of sustainable crops and **Ploutos project** that aims to rebalance agri-food value chains towards supporting them in their transition as environmentally, socially and socially sustainable systems. Finally, the **AgroApps 360°** integrated solution for precision farming was presented. This service provides high-accuracy weather forecasting, threat and infection alerts, irrigation planning, application of fertilisers and pesticides, as well as automated task management, among other functionalities. The solution leverages satellite, meteorological and in-situ data, and supports interconnection with IoT devices and agricultural infrastructure for advanced precision.

Figure 21: Snapshot from the presentation of AgroApps PC

3.1.7 Conclusion and upcoming activities

The final presentation was focused on the future steps of the agroBRIDGES project that might be of interest for local producers, farmers and agri-food chain actors, with most important being the launch of the agroBRIDGES toolbox and national roll-out activities. In the end, attendees were provided with the feedback form to evaluate the event and the session was closed.

Figure 22: Presentation of upcoming activities of agroBRIDGES

Due to difficulties in setting up one-to-one meetings, in parallel with presentations at the main stage, the networking area remained available on the next day, from 11:00 – 16:00 (local time) for attendees to reschedule cancelled meetings or book additional ones.

3.2 Event participation

Initially, approximately 80 people registered online for the online networking event, most of them being producers from various areas of Greece. The online registration form was closed before the deadline, as the event's maximum capacity supported 50 people.

However, in the second step of registration, a total of 35 people registered by creating an online profile on the matchmaking platform, including speakers and the organising team. The breakdown of participants is presented in the following table.

Table 3: Event attendees

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	14
Branding company (Speaker)	1
B2B sales platform (Speaker)	2
Technology provider (Speaker)	1
Organising team	2
Total	20

On the day of the event, participation ranged from 12 – 20 participants over the duration of the event. Most of the time, 18 – 20 attendees were present in the main stage. The matchmaking platform does not support detailed attendance statistics for the networking area.

In the networking area, **8 meeting requests** were submitted by participants, out of which 6 were agreed. The matchmaking platform does not support statistics on the outcome of the meetings, i.e. if they happened or not. There were 2 known cases in which one party did not show up to the one-to-one meeting.

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

The event evaluation form was circulated to attendees during the final session of the event, and also immediately after the end. **2 responses were submitted**, which is a small sample to extract quantitative results. Qualitative feedback that was provided by attendees and speakers is worth mentioning, however.

- Participants could not find enough people, interesting for them to network with, which is attributed to the high level of segmentation in terms of product types and location. One attendee mentioned that a potential solution would be to organise the event at a larger scale.
- Participants could not find business opportunities with customers in the HORECA business and other value chain actors and reported miscommunication of the event scope. This outcome may be attributed to: (i) the interest of producers on business agreements with other value chain actors, rather than knowledge exchange with peers, (ii) participation was predominantly from producers and farmers, while HORECA and other value chain actors were not represented.
- Several participants expressed interest on the event presentations, before and after the event. Due to the limited number of available positions, it was decided that event sessions will be recorded and uploaded online to be shared via the promotional channels employed for the event. A recommendation was made to have more in-depth content during company presentations.
- Interaction of participants with the speakers and the organisers was quite low and may be attributed to the lack of a tour-de-table session to motivate attendees to speak about their business and products. However, a tour-de-table is only recommended if there is a small number of attendees, and enough time is foreseen in the programme for this interaction.
- Several participants experienced difficulties in registering to the online matchmaking platform, including the fact that the participants' interface (e.g., log in / registration) was not entirely translated in Greek. The problem was partially resolved with the use of a step-by-step guide introduced in **Section 2.3.2** and technical support offered via email and phone calls.
- Participants experienced difficulty in reading the content of presentations during the event, which was attributed to the conferencing tool used for sessions, which reduced content size as more participants entered the room.
- Some participants did not show up after setting up one-to-one meetings. This may be attributed to missing functionalities of the online matchmaking platform. For instance, information about who is online is not included. The platform does not support reminders for upcoming one-to-one meetings a few minutes before they start. Notifications are not sent to the other party when the first participant arrives to a networking room.
- Speakers reported having a positive experience during the event and encouraged the audience to reach out for questions after the event.

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organisation?

Online networking / matchmaking events can be promising for the agri-food sector, as they overcome physical limitations of producers and agri-food actors to meet other businesses that otherwise they wouldn’t know of. However, one important limitation is that the networking process is hard to be replicated online, which in physical format is quite natural and quick-paced, entails several steps and can be quite hard for producers not familiar with such tools. Also, there is a lack of networking platforms addressing the Greek market, that excludes participants who do not speak English. Repetition of such events could mitigate such barriers, as people seem quite eager to overcome such barriers and experience could be built.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

If such event was to be organised again in the region, it would require a large and highly motivated community of regional actors, spanning the whole agri-food value chain, but similar events should either be narrower in scope, or focus on specific product or involve participants from specific geographic locations, to generate more matches. Due to the technical requirements that create friction with participants, physical organisation would be preferred in the future. The concept was a quite interesting experience though.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

The main barriers and limitations faced are closely related to the issues outlined in the previous sections with the two most important reiterated below:

- The event requires balanced representation of diverse actors in the value chain and product types, which can be challenging to have control over, because people are registering in the platform gradually. People joining the platform early have access to limited number of profiles and can lose interest quite easily.
- The organisation of the event required intense technical support for attendees and speakers in a limited timeframe, which can be hard to provide as people join from different devices, have different digital literacy levels and reproduction of the steps requires careful communication.

5. Conclusions - Summary

The “Let’s build our SFSC” online networking and matchmaking event for producers, agri-food chain actors and HORECA was organised in Greece by Q-PLAN on March 2nd, 2023. The event lasted for 2.5 hours and was supported by the online matchmaking platform chosen by the agroBRIDGES consortium, following market research performed in Task 3.4.

The event schedule was split in two axes, the first being webinar-style sessions, starting with an introduction to the agroBRIDGES project and the event, followed by an open discussion about SFSC business models in Greece and featuring presentations of 3 successful companies supporting the agrifood sector. The second axis was the networking area that offered attendees the opportunity to network with other businesses all over Greece. The networking section lasted for 1 hour and three networking slots were offered to each participant, in parallel with company presentations at the main stage.

80 individuals registered for the event, following the event promotion on social media and professional networks, out of which 35 people created online networking profiles on the matchmaking platform. On the day of the event, approximately 20 people joined the event, and 8 one-to-one meetings were booked.

The concept of online networking and matchmaking shows a lot of promise but requires several improvements to be successful for the Greek agri-food market and SFSCs specifically, including: (i) narrower scope, (ii) considerable effort to build a balanced and engaged community of value chain actors, and finally (iii) close collaboration with attendees to overcome technical difficulties that may get easier if the event is organised more frequently.

Annex – Full results of the open discussion on SFSC business models

Table 4: Summary of the open discussion about SFSC business models

Question	Direct Sales	Local food stores	Online sales
Examples	Open farms Open markets Exhibitions and fairs	Specialised local food stores Stores managed by producers' associations Dedicated sales points in supermarkets	Producers' e-shop E-commerce platforms for local food products
Can it be successful in Greece?	<p>Yes, a necessary tool for producers, but must be used in combination.</p> <p>Open farms: Successful for wine and grapes, supports direct sales and getting to know the producers.</p> <p>Open markets: Supported interaction of consumers with the producer / products especially in organic crops.</p> <p>Exhibitions: Gained a lot of ground before the COVID-19 pandemic. A successful example was the Gourmet Exhibition in Thessaloniki that offered the chance for small-scale producers.</p>	<p>Specialised food stores: Mostly for small-scale producer to promote their products.</p> <p>Stores managed by producer associations: Mostly for larger-scale producers, supporting the organisation of supply.</p> <p>Supermarket dedicated segments: The most promising business opportunity for this business model.</p>	<p>Platforms have great potential for agrifood products and high growth in Greece and abroad. Platforms are expected to become the norm in the future agri-food market.</p> <p>Producers' e-shops can be viable if linked / connected to a digital marketplace, similar to Skroutz in Greece.</p>
Main benefits	<p>Consumers get to know the producer and products better.</p> <p>Direct sales introduce benefits on their own but work best when used in combination with digital promotion / digital sales channels.</p>	<p>Supermarket dedicated segments enable producers to reach to a wider market and sell larger quantities, as supermarkets usually have stores in multiple locations.</p>	<p>Platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide consumers with a wider choice of products at the same place. - Consumers also benefit from lower prices due to lower involvement of intermediaries. - Producers are supported by the platform for marketing and sales, allowing

Question	Direct Sales	Local food stores	Online sales
			<p>them time to focus more on production.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Producers can reach to a wider market and even export products. - Producers can freely set the minimum quantity ordered through the platform. - Platforms reduce producers' reliance on value chain intermediaries. - Platforms enhance sustainability, i.e. from reduced food waste (est. 10 – 30% reduction, Source: Wikifarmer)
Main drawbacks	<p>Direct sales are focused on the production; Marketing, sales and branding techniques are not utilised.</p>	<p>Supermarket point of sales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher competition among products, due to limited space - Hard to agree on contracts, supply methods vary among stores and require large quantities. 	<p>Online sales do not support interaction of the consumer with the producer and the product.</p> <p>Producer e-shops can be costly for the producer, as they require development / maintenance, raising the costs.</p>
Profitability	<p>Up to 50% profit margin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower transportation, preservation effort and costs. - Lower capital, financing & overhead costs. 	<p>Up to 20% profit margin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher production volume reduces margins, due to higher overhead and capital costs for logistics. - The intermediary brings considerable value – in exchange for lower profit margin, but increased benefit. 	<p>Up to 300% increase in profit margins:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible price-setting by the producer - Minimum number of intermediaries <p>Source: Wikifarmer</p>